

Solute Reflection and Transmission in Composite Membranes

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Solute rejection and transmission characteristics of composite membranes have been investigated. Series and parallel arrangements have been considered. The efficiency of energy conversion when hydrodynamic and diffusional flux are coupled has also been examined.

In a previous communication¹ we discussed reflection characteristics of membranes for non-interacting and interacting solute-solvent systems. Natural membranes are not as simple as envisaged in this study. Chemical and ultramicroscopic evidence indicates that biological membranes are made up of contiguous layers² of substances differing in composition and permeation characteristics. A typical example of double membrane system is the epithelial cell bounded on either side with liquid of different permeability properties³.

In the present study the solute rejection and solute transmission by composite membranes arranged in series and in parallel have been examined. Coupling characteristics have also been studied.

The rate of volumetric flux, J_v , and diffusional flux, J_D , under the simultaneous action of a hydrostatic pressure difference, ΔP , and osmotic pressure difference, $\Delta\pi$, on the basis of non-equilibrium thermodynamic theory are expressed as⁴ :

$$J_v = L_{11}\Delta P + L_{12}\Delta\pi \quad \dots (1)$$

$$J_D = L_{21}\Delta P + L_{22}\Delta\pi \quad \dots (2)$$

L 's are the phenomenological coefficients.

The ability of a membrane to reject and transmit a solute is expressed in terms of reflection coefficient, σ , and solute permeability, ω , defined as ;

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta\pi} \right] J_v = 0 \quad \dots (3)$$

and

$$\omega = \left[\frac{J_s}{\Delta\pi} \right] J_v = 0 \quad \dots (4)$$

where, J_s , denotes the solute flux.

coefficient and solute permeability of its component parts. We obtain such relationships for the parallel and the series arrangements.

Parallel Arrangement : Let us consider two membranes A and B which are arranged in parallel to form a composite membrane. When two solutions of unequal concentrations separate each of these membranes separately, their reflection coefficients may be defined as ;

$$\sigma_A = \left[\frac{\Delta P_A}{\Delta\pi} \right] (J_v)_A = 0 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\sigma_B = \left[\frac{\Delta P_B}{\Delta\pi} \right] (J_v)_B = 0 \quad \dots (6)$$

ΔP_A and ΔP_B are the steady state hydrostatic pressure differences developed across the component membrane under the action of the same osmotic pressure difference $\Delta\pi$. The volumetric flux, J_v , in each case occurs under the simultaneous action of the gradients of the chemical potentials of the solute and the solvent so that we may write¹

$$(J_v)_A = \bar{V}_s \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta\mu_s} \cdot \Delta\mu_s + \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial (J_w)_A}{\partial \Delta\mu_w} \cdot \Delta\mu_w \quad \dots (7)$$

$$(J_v)_B = \bar{V}_s \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta\mu_s} \cdot \Delta\mu_s + \bar{V}_w \frac{\partial (J_w)_B}{\partial \Delta\mu_w} \cdot \Delta\mu_w \quad \dots (8)$$

and

$$(J_v)_{cp} = \gamma_A (J_v)_A + \gamma_B (J_v)_B \quad \dots (9)$$

γ_A and γ_B are fractional areas occupied by membranes A and B respectively. Subscript cp denotes the composite membrane arranged in parallel.

The solute rejection and transmission of a composite membrane will be related to the reflection

Using equations (7), (8) and (9) the reflection coefficient for the composite membrane may be

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written as ;

$$\sigma = - \frac{\left[\gamma_A \left\{ \frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} - \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right\} \right]}{\left[\gamma_A \left\{ \frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right\} \right]} + \frac{\left[\gamma_B \left\{ \frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} - \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right\} \right]}{\left[\gamma_B \left\{ \frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right\} \right]} \quad \dots (10)$$

In the derivation of the above expression following relations⁵

$$\Delta \mu_s = \bar{V}_s \Delta P + \frac{\Delta \pi}{C_s} \quad \dots (11)$$

and

$$\Delta \mu_\omega = \bar{V}_\omega (\Delta P - \Delta \pi) \quad \dots (12)$$

have also been used.

The reflection coefficients for the component membranes accordingly become ;

$$\sigma_A = - \frac{\left[\frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} - \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]}{\left[\frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]} \quad \dots (13)$$

$$\sigma_B = - \frac{\left[\frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} - \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]}{\left[\frac{\bar{V}_s}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_\omega)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]} \quad \dots (14)$$

On the basis of non-equilibrium thermodynamic theory, it is possible to write volumetric fluxes in terms of phenomenological equations when steady osmotic pressure differences are developed as ;

$$(J_v)_A = (L_{11})_A (\Delta P)_A + (L_{12})_A \Delta \pi = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$(J_v)_B = (L_{11})_B (\Delta P)_B + (L_{12})_B \Delta \pi = 0 \quad \dots (16)$$

$$(J_v)_{cp} = (L_{11})_{cp} \Delta P + (L_{12})_{cp} \Delta \pi = 0 \quad (17)$$

It may be noted that, ΔP , $(\Delta P)_A$ and $(\Delta P)_B$ in the parallel arrangement will be related as ;

$$\frac{\Delta P}{\sigma} = \frac{(\Delta P)_A}{\sigma_A} = \frac{(\Delta P)_B}{\sigma_B} \quad \dots (18)$$

Using equations (15), (16), (17) and (9) we find that ;

$$\sigma = \gamma_A \sigma_A \frac{(L_{11})_A}{(L_{11})_{cp}} + \gamma_B \sigma_B \frac{(L_{11})_B}{(L_{11})_{cp}} \quad \dots (19)$$

The above relationship can easily be obtained using equations (10), (13) and (14) as well the ratio

$\frac{(L_{11})_A}{(L_{11})_{cp}}$ and $\frac{(L_{11})_B}{(L_{11})_{cp}}$ may be called fractional filtration coefficients for membranes *A* and *B* respectively.

In a general case when *n* component membranes are arranged in parallel, we may write ;

$$\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i \sigma_i \frac{(L_{11})_i}{(L_{11})_{cp}} \quad \dots (20)$$

Equation (19) clearly shows that if ideal semipermeable membranes are arranged in parallel, the composite membrane will exhibit ideal behaviour only when $(L_{11})_{cp} = (L_{11})_A = (L_{11})_B$.

Solute transmission : Solute flux, J_s , across the composite membrane separating two solutions of different concentrations may be expressed as ;

$$J_s = \gamma_A (J_s)_A + \gamma_B (J_s)_B \quad \dots (21)$$

$$J_s = \left[\gamma_A \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \gamma_B \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \right] \Delta \mu_s \quad \dots (22)$$

where $(J_s)_A$ and $(J_s)_B$ are solute fluxes through component membranes and are given by ;

$$(J_s)_A = \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \Delta \mu_s \quad \dots (23)$$

$$(J_s)_B = \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \Delta \mu_s \quad \dots (24)$$

Equation (22) using equation (11) may be written as ;

$$J_s = \bar{V}_s \left[\gamma_A \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \gamma_B \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \right] \Delta P + \frac{\Delta \pi}{C_s} \left[\gamma_A \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \gamma_B \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \right] \quad \dots (25)$$

The solute permeability, ω , is thus given by,

$$\omega = \left(\bar{V}_s \sigma + \frac{1}{C_s} \right) \left[\gamma_A \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} + \gamma_B \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \right] \quad \dots (26)$$

The solute permeability of the component membranes may be expressed as ;

$$\omega_A = \left[\frac{(J_s)_A}{\Delta \pi} \right]_{J_v=0} = \left(\bar{V}_s \sigma_A + \frac{1}{C_s} \right) \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \quad \dots (27)$$

and

$$\omega_B = \left[\frac{(J_s)_B}{\Delta \pi} \right]_{J_v=0} = \left(\bar{V}_s \sigma_B + \frac{1}{C_s} \right) \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \quad (28)$$

From equations (26), (27) and (28) one gets,

$$\frac{\omega}{\sigma} = \gamma_A \frac{\omega_A}{\sigma_A} + \gamma_B \frac{\omega_B}{\sigma_B} + \frac{\gamma_A}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{1}{\sigma_A} \right) + \frac{\gamma_B}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{1}{\sigma_B} \right) \quad \dots (29)$$

when solute and solvent do not interact during transmission.

There are instances when it is not possible to ignore interactions between a solute and a solvent when passing through a membrane. The extent of interactions depends on the nature of the system⁶. When an aqueous solution flows through a mosaic membrane the solute and the solvent interact very weakly and follow different paths. Higher interaction occurs when flow of a solution occurs through a coarse capillary membrane. For an interacting system using the procedure outlined above it is possible to show that ;

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\omega}{\sigma} &= \gamma_A \frac{\omega_A}{\sigma_A} + \gamma_B \frac{\omega_B}{\sigma_B} + \frac{\gamma_A}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{1}{\sigma_A} \right) \\ &+ \frac{\gamma_B}{C_s} \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu_s} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{1}{\sigma_B} \right) - \gamma_A \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_A}{\partial \Delta \mu \omega} \\ &\left(\frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{1}{\sigma_A} \right) - \gamma_B \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_B}{\partial \Delta \mu \omega} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma} - \frac{1}{\sigma_B} \right) \quad \dots (30) \end{aligned}$$

For an ideal semipermeable composite parallel membrane when $\sigma = \sigma_A = \sigma_B = 1$, equations (29) and (30) reduce to ;

$$\omega = \gamma_A \omega_A + \gamma_B \omega_B.$$

Comparison of equations (26) and (27) show that last two terms in equation (27) occur due to the interaction of the solute and solvent. Furthermore, the ratio of $\frac{\omega}{\sigma}$ will always be less when solute and solvent interact during transmission.

Series Arrangement : Composite membranes containing component membranes arranged in series are of considerable interest⁷. They exhibit phenomena neither exhibited by component parts nor by the parallel arrangement and occur in the living systems⁷. The forces acting across the series membrane are additive so that we may write ;

$$\Delta P = [\Delta P]_A + [\Delta P]_B \quad \dots (31)$$

and

$$\Delta \pi = [\Delta \pi]_A + [\Delta \pi]_B \quad \dots (32)$$

The subscript C_s denotes the composite system arranged in series. ΔP is the total osmotic pressure. $[\Delta P]_A$ and $[\Delta P]_B$ are the osmotic pressures acting across membrane A and B in the composite system. Using equations (31), (32), (5) and (6) it can be shown that the reflection coefficient of the composite membrane and the constituents arranged in series are related as ;

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i \Delta \pi_i = \sigma \Delta \pi \quad \dots (33)$$

Using relationships (26), (27), (28) and

$$J_s = (J_s)_A = (J_s)_B.$$

When steady solute flux across the composite membrane occurs, it can easily be shown⁷ that

$$\frac{1}{\omega} = \frac{1}{\omega_A} + \frac{1}{\omega_B}$$

Efficiency of Energy conversion :

Kedem and Caplan⁸ have defined a dimensionless parameter called degree of coupling using phenomenological description of coupled processes. When volumetric flux and diffusional flux occur simultaneously, the coupling coefficient, 'q' is expressed as ;

$$q = \frac{L_{12}}{\sqrt{L_{11} L_{22}}}$$

The solute permeability through a membrane may be related to coupling coefficient as ;

$$\omega = C_s^- L_{22} (1 - q^2) \quad \dots (34)$$

since⁹

$$\omega = C_s^- (L_{11} L_{22} - L_{12}^2) / L_{11}$$

The solute permeabilities of membranes A and B accordingly are

$$\omega_A = C_s^- (L_{22})_A (1 - q_A^2) \quad \dots (35)$$

$$\omega_B = C_s^- (L_{22})_B (1 - q_B^2) \quad \dots (36)$$

For parallel arrangement ;

$$\omega = \gamma_A \omega_A + \gamma_B \omega_B$$

Using equations (34), (35) and (36) we may write

$$(1 - q_{cp}^2) = \gamma_A \frac{(L_{22})_A}{(L_{22})_{cp}} (1 - q_A^2) + \gamma_B \frac{(L_{22})_B}{(L_{22})_{cp}} (1 - q_B^2) \quad \dots (37)$$

For a series arrangement ;

$$\frac{1}{\omega} = \frac{1}{\omega_A} + \frac{1}{\omega_B}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{1}{(1 - q_{cp}^2)} = \frac{(L_{22})_{cp}}{(L_{22})_A} \frac{1}{(1 - q_A^2)} + \frac{(L_{22})_{cp}}{(L_{22})_B} \frac{1}{(1 - q_B^2)} \quad \dots (38)$$

η_{max} , the efficiency of maximum energy conversion for any coupled process is related with the coupling coefficient⁸

$$\eta_{max} = \frac{q^2}{(1 + \sqrt{1 - q^2})^2} \quad \dots (39)$$

Under certain simplifying assumptions it is possible to compare, η_{max} , for the parallel and the series arrangement. For instance, when we put $\gamma_A = \gamma_B$

and $(L_{22})_A = (L_{22})_B$ we find equation(37) becomes

$$q^2_{cp} = \frac{1}{2}(q_A^2 + q_B^2) \quad \dots (40)$$

since

$$(L_{22})_{cp} = \nu_A(L_{22})_A + \nu_B(L_{22})_B$$

For the series arrangement

$$\frac{1}{(L_{22})_{cs}} = \frac{1}{(L_{22})_A} + \frac{1}{(L_{22})_B} \quad \dots (41)$$

so that equation (38) may be expressed as

$$\frac{2}{(1 - q^2_{cs})} = \frac{1}{(1 - q_A^2)} + \frac{1}{(1 - q_B^2)} \quad \dots (42)$$

when we put $(L_{22})_A = (L_{22})_B$.

For the purpose of comparison we consider a typical case

when $q_A = 1/2$ and $q_B = 1/4$ so that

$$(\eta_{\max})_A = 0.072 \quad (\eta_{\max})_B = 0.016.$$

Furthermore, $q_{cp} = 0.390$, and $q_{cs} = 0.420$.

Putting the values of q_{cp} and q_{cs} in equation(39) we find that

$$(\eta_{\max})_{cp} = 0.041$$

$$(\eta_{\max})_{cs} = 0.050$$

Series arrangement thus yields greater η_{\max} . It may be noted that this is a general conclusion independent of the q_A and q_B values chosen.

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